

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

[D4.3 IPSP Guidelines]

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DISCLAIMER

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

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Version history

Version	Created/Modified	Comments
0.0	Authors	First draft
0.1	Authors	Draft for review
1.0	Authors	Final draft

Acronyms

CAP	Common Access Point
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution Licence
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DCH	Diamond Capacity Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing for Diamond Open Access
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Provider
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
OA	Open Access
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
SIGs	Special Interest Groups
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This report outlines the development of the Institutional Publisher Service Providers (IPSP) Guidelines, a deliverable of DIAMAS Task 4.3. The guidelines build on existing resources and previous outputs from the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects, and aim to provide comprehensive instructions to help IPSPs meet current standards for Diamond Open Access(OA)publishing, as defined in the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS)(Consortium of the DIAMAS Project, 2024).

Following an extensive analysis of resources, 18 thematic areas were identified, based on their relevance across diverse publishing practices and challenges as well as their potential to enhance the credibility, efficiency, and capacity of IPSPs. These topics align with the seven core components of the DOAS, and correspond to the scope and contents of the forthcoming IPSP Toolsuite (D4.3).

The guidelines were collaboratively drafted by DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA partners and reviewed by the Toolsuite Editorial Board. To ensure accessibility for a broader audience, the guidelines have been translated into Spanish, Portuguese, and Croatian and will be integrated into the DIAMAS Common Access Point (CAP) as part of the online IPSP Toolsuite.

The guidelines will be regularly updated with new resources and tools to ensure they remain current and continue to support best practices in OA publishing.

1. Introduction

This report describes the process behind the creation of the Institutional Publisher Service Providers (IPSP) Guidelines that are the primary output of the DIAMAS Task 4.3 “IPSP Guidelines”. The main objective of this task is to produce a set of comprehensive documents that offer detailed instructions and practical guidance to assist IPSPs in meeting current standards, outlined as the seven core components of the DIAMAS deliverable *Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) for diamond open access* (Rico-Castro et al., 2024).

To ensure accessibility for a broader audience, the guidelines will be integrated into the DIAMAS Common Access Point (CAP) as part of the IPSP Toolsuite (currently under development) – a component of the CAP that gives access to resources and tools facilitating the implementation of standards; additionally, the guidelines have been translated into Spanish, Portuguese, and Croatian

The report details the applied methodology, the writing and review workflows, as well as the framework used for translation. Aspects related to the technical development and the sustainability of the online component that will host the guidelines will be further addressed in the forthcoming report on the IPSP Toolsuite (D4.2, due in October 2024).

The report and the translated guidelines are available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13786094>

2. Description of the IPSP Guidelines

2.1 Methodology and structure

The IPSP guidelines task (T4.3) began in month six of the DIAMAS project (February 2023). The task focuses on the development of resources that will guide IPSPs during the implementation of best practices and standards. The guidelines build on existing resources with relevant scope, earlier outputs of the DIAMAS (2024) and CRAFT-OA (2024) projects, and an extensive analysis of identified gaps and challenges.

Collecting relevant information was a critical step in ensuring that the guidelines are evidence-based, comprehensive, and grounded in current best practices. The following documentation was consulted during this preparatory stage:

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Open Access Journals Toolkit: The Open Access Journals Toolkit (DOAJ & OASPA, 2024) provides guidance for both new and established open access journals, covering a wide range of topics such as governance, policies, financing, and technical aspects.

DIAMAS Survey results (Armengou et al., 2023) and the **DIAMAS report on the gap analysis results** (Brun, 2023): these project outputs were essential for identifying the current state of play in Open Access (OA) publishing. The processed survey results provided direct feedback from stakeholders, whereas the gap analysis provided examples of challenges faced by IPSPs, and identified specific areas in need of further development.

Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) V1.0: Version 1 of EQSIP (Armengou, Redhead, & Rooryck, 2023) was used as a point of reference against which IPSPs may be compared. This was done in conjunction with the IPSP Toolsuite task, which used the core components of EQSIP as the basis for its structure. Version 2.0 of EQSIP has now been renamed as the **Diamond OA Standard (DOAS)** (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024), and that new version is referenced in the guidelines and will be used as the basis for future iterations of the guidelines.

Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of FAIR Principles (Armengou et al., 2023): the report offers an overview of the technical standards and best publishing practices and is intended to serve as reference for IPSPs and IPTPs (Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Providers).

Report on challenges and help measures faced by OA journals and platforms (Laakso, 2024): a gap analysis, assessing the alignment of Diamond OA journals with recommended technical best practices outlined in the abovementioned report.

The next step was to synthesise the findings into a coherent set of guidelines. The information was organised into thematic areas. It was decided to use the seven core components of DOAS, so that the guidelines would also align with the structure and subject coverage of the Toolsuite. This ensured that the guidelines would also interlink with the Toolsuite articles and the design of the CAP.

Eighteen (18) topics were identified based on their practical applicability across diverse publishing contexts and their potential to enhance the credibility, efficiency, and capacity of IPSPs. A brief overview of the topics and contents of the guidelines is provided below (see Annex 1 for the complete guidelines):

- 1) **Revenue Streams:** these guidelines provide an overview of the diverse funding mechanisms for Diamond OA, and a framework to ensure transparency.
- 2) **Diamond OA policies:** these guidelines facilitate the implementation of Diamond OA policies in academic publishing, emphasising the importance of accessibility, quality, and transparency.
- 3) **Implementing community-led governance in publishing services:** These guidelines outline how to establish clear processes, policies, and structures to implement community-led governance in publishing services, ensuring regulated operations and decision-making.
- 4) **Copyright, authors' rights policy:** these guidelines present basic concepts related to copyright as well as best practices in defining and displaying copyright policies for editors and publishers.
- 5) **Use of open licences in open access publishing:** guidelines for using open licences and distributing scholarly works.
- 6) **Research data sharing policy:** these guidelines help IPSPs implement a research data sharing policy, recognising the essential role of underlying research data in supporting conclusions and reproducibility.
- 7) **Preprints:** these guidelines identify good practices with regard to the publication of preprints that are already available on preprint servers and/or open repositories.
- 8) **Self-archiving policy:** these guidelines describe the essential elements of a self-archiving policy.
- 9) **Handling negative research results:** these guidelines outline a publisher-level policy regarding the publication of negative or unexpected scientific results and data.
- 10) **Availability of research protocols, methods and software:** these guidelines describe measures to ensure that all research protocols, methods, and software are publicly available, accessible, and reproducible.
- 11) **Basic editorial information that should be displayed:** these guidelines outline the details of policies and procedures that should be displayed on a Publisher's website.
- 12) **GDPR and Personal data:** these guidelines explain how IPSPs should handle personal information and comply with relevant regulations.
- 13) **Choosing a platform:** these guidelines help IPSPs understand their technical needs and factors to be considered when choosing an online publication platform.
- 14) **Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent:** these guidelines help IPSPs implement requirements and recommendations regarding metadata and full-text formats.
- 15) **Marketing, communication and visibility:** these guidelines help IPSPs meet requirements regarding visibility and discoverability, and introduce communication and marketing strategies.
- 16) **Usage and metrics:** these guidelines facilitate the implementation of comprehensive, accurate, and reliable usage and metric indicators.

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17) **Gender diversity:** these guidelines describe a framework for IPSPs to integrate gender equity into their activities.

18) **Multilingualism:** these guidelines provide some practical suggestions to help IPSPs integrate multilingualism into their activities.

2.2 Writing process

The writing process began with the assignment of lead authors and co-authors for each identified topic. The lead authors were selected among the members of the writing teams who had previously contributed to the IPSP Toolsuite, the DOAS, and other resources consulted during the analysis preceding the drafting of the guidelines.

Lead authors were provided with a template (see Annex 2), and asked to prioritise use of project-generated content and of external resources available with a Creative Commons CC BY licence, to ensure that the guidelines can be reused, updated, and translated as needed. Authors were also encouraged to include references, additional reading materials, and tips that would support the practical implementation of the guidelines. Additionally, discipline-specific aspects and instructions were added, where applicable.

The first drafts of the guidelines were circulated among the work package partners for internal review.

The guidelines were then compiled into a single document and forwarded to the Toolsuite Editorial Board for feedback. The comments and suggestions made during this initial review round resulted in significant revisions. Once the final drafts were approved by the writing teams, the guidelines underwent a thorough copy-edit to ensure consistency in terminology, referencing style, and tone.

2.3 Editorial Board and external review

As part of the project's co-creation activities, a campaign was launched in June 2023, with an aim to engage the community in identifying resources that would feed into the IPSP Toolsuite (D4.2) and the guidelines. The campaign also included a call for expression of interest to review the content of these resources. In response, an Editorial Board was formed and provided feedback¹.

¹ The process of assembling the Editorial Board and conducting the review will be addressed in more detail in the forthcoming deliverable D4.2 "IPSP Toolsuite" (M26).

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Following the internal review, the guidelines were submitted to the members of the Editorial Board for feedback. Their suggested improvements were incorporated into the final version of the guidelines. This process is detailed in D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite.

Several guidelines were collaboratively developed through active discussions with partners leading relevant tasks in the CRAFT-OA project, alongside two OPERAS Special Interest Groups (SIGs)—the Best Practices SIG and the OA Business Models SIG (OPERAS, n.d.)—highlighting the importance of this co-creation process.

2.4 Translations

As correct and reliable translation is time-consuming, we needed to be restrictive with regards to the number of languages the guidelines would be translated to at this stage. The criteria for selecting languages included adherence to the foreseen task timeline and the availability of native-speaking partners, with a good command of English and expertise in the topics covered. Based on these criteria, it was decided that the initial release of the guidelines would be translated into Spanish, Croatian and Portuguese.

The articles were drafted in simple language, avoiding technical terminology. This helped with translating the guidelines with the use of already established terms in languages other than English.

To facilitate the translation, it was decided to use the pilot translation service [Mondaecus](#) (Da Silva Ferreira & Silva, 2023, Silva, 2024), an online platform developed by the University of Coimbra that offers a range of features enabling author teams to work collaboratively. In order to assess the feasibility of translating the guidelines (approx. 20.000 words in total) within a short time period, the authors tested the functionalities and workflow of the platform. The guidelines on Multilingualism were also chosen as a use case in a Mutual Learning Exercise for the OPERAS SIGs, during which participants were asked to use the platform to translate the text in their native language.

The team of developers presented the platform's main functionalities to project partners, and provided guidance and support throughout the translation process. At the time of the guidelines' translation, Mondaecus was at the alpha testing phase. It was decided that use of the platform would be mutually beneficial to both parties.

Project partners contributing to the translation were organised into teams, with a lead author assigned to each language. Since Mondaecus supports collaborative workflows,

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each author was responsible for a specific section of the guidelines, and the final drafts were collectively reviewed.

Fig 1. Example of a Spanish translation in Mondaecus

The Mondaecus team promptly resolved minor technical issues that the translation teams identified throughout the process. Additionally, the DIAMAS team provided feedback and suggestions on the functionalities of the platform via a shared document. This reciprocal exchange proved beneficial for both parties, by facilitating the translation of the task outputs and identifying areas for further improvement of Mondaecus. As part of this collaborative process, the Mondaecus team further contributed by providing a Portuguese translation of the guidelines. The collaboration between Mondaecus and DIAMAS exemplifies a best practice in community-driven cooperation.

2.5 Technical implementation

The guidelines will be integrated into the CAP (currently under development), as part of the online IPSP Toolsuite. To this end, the design of the online component that will host the Toolsuite foresees pathways that ensure cross-referencing and integration of the guidelines with other related resources (such as the Toolsuite articles), and tools (for example, the Diamond OA self-assessment tool (FECYT, 2024). This process involves

embedding hyperlinks and references within the content to enable access from/to relevant sections of the CAP, including those components that will be integrated at a later stage (e.g. the CRAFT-OA Living Handbook). Additionally, we will implement a schedule for regular updates to incorporate new resources and tools as they become available, ensuring that the online component remains current.

In the first instance, there will be three ways to access the guidelines. The documentation will be available in a designated section within the CAP. Additionally, links to specific guidelines will be provided within relevant articles in the Toolsuite as well as in the corresponding DOAS sections of the self-assessment tool. This integration will support users by providing practical guidance as they navigate the DOAS components within the Toolsuite and/or assess their compliance to the suggested standards.

2.6 Feedback and revisions

Collaboration and coordination of the writing process: several related outputs were being developed simultaneously. To ensure that the guidelines aligned with the DOAS and offered concrete instructions on applying the recommendations found in the Toolsuite articles, we involved partners who contributed to these key project resources. Assigning lead authors from the teams responsible for delivering the DOAS and IPSP Toolsuite articles facilitated the writing process. The lead authors were responsible for preparing drafts, and the writing teams responded with comments and suggestions.

Challenges: One of the main challenges faced by the author teams was developing guidelines that covered the wide scope of topics in the DOAS and IPSP Toolsuite. Another challenge was adapting the guidelines to varying publishing workflows, emerging practices (e.g., data sharing) and specific standards (e.g., metadata standards). To address this, we conducted two review rounds: by the consortium partners and the Editorial Board. The diverse backgrounds and collective expertise of the reviewers helped in drafting targeted instructions.

Content format and translations: The survey responses and gap analysis indicate that These measures should capture the academic influence through citations and the broader societal impact through downloads, mentions, and engagement on various platforms. Most IPSPs have limited technical capacity and relatively low compliance with current standards. Thus, it was decided that the guidelines template would have a simple structure, including a brief section that introduces each topic and a practical, action-oriented main article to help IPSPs understand and implement best practices. Where possible, short tips that would lead to immediate improvements were included, along with a classification of the guidelines based on the resources and effort needed for

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implementation (see, for example, the guidelines on multilingualism and gender equity). The “further reading” section lists resources that help IPSPs have a broad understanding of each topic.

The translation teams have identified the following functionalities that would help manage editorial workflows and bulk translations with the use of online platforms, such as Mondaecus:

- Memory record feature: The platforms could store frequently corrected terms across different languages and contexts (e.g., remembering that “quick-win” is translated as “X” in Portuguese and “Y” in Spanish).
- Track changes: a functionality that tracks changes made in both the original text and the translated version.
- Export options: variable export formats (e.g., Word documents) that retain formatting and hyperlinks, offering a more flexible output.

2.7 Sustainability and further developments planned

As will be further explained in the forthcoming D4.2 “IPSP Toolsuite”, procedures will be established to define the frequency of revisions, while version control will be documented through a detailed log of all changes. As part of the online Toolsuite, the guidelines will be maintained by partners contributing to the DIAMAS Common Access Point, that will be further developed as the European Diamond Capacity Hub (DCH), and deliver support, tools, services to Diamond OA capacity centres and other stakeholders. Accordingly, the responsibility for future updates or additional translations of the guidelines will be assigned to the DCH. It has been decided that French will be the next language for translation

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4. Annex 1: Guidelines

1) Revenue Streams

Lead author(s)
Johan Rooryck
Contributor(s)
Peer reviewer(s)
Elio Pellin, Tobias Steiner, Laura Rincón
Introduction
<p>These guidelines provide an overview of the diverse funding mechanisms for Diamond OA, and a framework to ensure transparency and maintain trust, in alignment with the values of the disciplines served by scholarly Publishers.</p>
Body
<p>A Diamond OA publisher is typically funded via <i>public funding</i>. Public funding can be <i>directly</i> provided to the Diamond OA publisher by a parent institution or a public body in the form of a regular annual contribution or via project funding. It can also be provided <i>indirectly</i> via the salaries of people who fulfil other tasks at the parent institution in addition to their work for the IP.</p> <p>In addition to public funding, IPs may rely on income that reaches them via diverse <i>revenue streams</i>. These include, but are not limited to, income from print-on-demand services, editorial services not related to Diamond OA journals, or Voluntary Author Contributions (VAC). Voluntary Author Contributions are permitted as a revenue stream, as long as it is clearly indicated on the website at the journal level that delivered publication services are not contingent on the payment of any fees by the authors. For an example see the journal Glossa Psycholinguistics' policy on VACs, or that of the Open Library of Humanities.</p> <p>The <i>Diamond Open Access Standard's (DOAS) Guidelines</i> make it clear that the origin of the revenue streams should be in line with the values, expectations, and traditions in the disciplines the Diamond OA publisher is serving. The nature of revenue streams should not have an impact on editorial independence. Editorial operations related to content and peer review are independent and free from influence from the bodies that financially support the</p>

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Diamond OA publisher or bodies that support individual publications of the Diamond OA publisher.

Any conflicts of interest between additional revenue streams (including commercial activity) and authors, reviewers or editors should be clearly indicated by the Diamond OA publisher on their website. Ideally, Diamond OA publishers also provide transparency on their funding via an explicit statement about the Diamond OA publisher’s funding streams on their website, where donations, project funding, in-kind contributions, and voluntary contributions are also acknowledged.

Discipline-specific considerations

The availability of revenue streams depends to a large extent on the specific scholarly (sub)disciplines served by the IP, the level of scholarly organisation of those (sub)disciplines, and the extent to which researchers and organisations in these (sub)disciplines have access to external funding. Diamond OA can be funded by the membership fees of scholarly societies if the relevant discipline is organised in that way.

Similarly, Voluntary Author Contributions (VACs) – are typically paid by authors with access to appropriate funds, either from their institution or extramural grants. While VACs can be a good redistributive mechanism (a VAC typically pays for the costs of more than one article), they are strongly dependent on the capacity of the specific discipline to capture grant money and the location and policies of the institutions that authors work for.

As a result, VACs may not be an appropriate revenue stream for all IPs. For example, due to its experimental nature, psycholinguistics attracts a fair amount of grant money, but the neighbouring discipline of descriptive linguistics of African languages is typically less well endowed with such grants.

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Further reading

These guidelines are available with a CC BY licence

2) Diamond OA policies

Lead author(s)
M ^a Ángeles Coslado
Contributor(s)
Virginia de Pablo
Peer reviewer(s)
Elio Pellin, Tobias Steiner, Laura Rincón
Introduction
<p>These guidelines facilitate the implementation of Diamond OA policies in academic publishing, emphasizing the importance of accessibility, quality, and transparency in disseminating scientific content.</p> <p>Diamond OA can be structured around a series of policies that enable efficient management of accessibility, quality, and transparency in knowledge dissemination. Diamond OA policies comprise elements such as free access, open licences, and peer review; appropriate open science practices; and clear technical management elements that ensure greater impact and enhanced visibility, using sustainable and efficient publishing models. Aligning editorial policies with these standards helps to improve research trustworthiness.</p>
Body
<p>Diamond OA policies in scholarly publishing encompass a wide spectrum of technical, and operational aspects that ensure compliance with the principles of Open Science and increase the trustworthiness of published research. The elements of a comprehensive OA policy can be summarized as follows:</p> <p>1. Access and Interoperability</p> <p>Ensuring equitable access to scientific content requires all publications to be freely available and interoperable.</p> <p>The development of a publishing infrastructure allows for streamlining editorial processes and ensuring efficient knowledge distribution. To achieve this, it is suggested that Diamond OA publishers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adopt interoperability and quality standards ● Use common metadata formats ● Apply metadata exchange protocols to ensure the semantic interoperability of scientific content

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- Use open-source technologies, with available open-source code

2. Quality in Peer Review Processes

Rigorous and transparent peer review is essential for academic excellence. Key aspects include:

- Publication and dissemination of the standards applied in content selection and a clear description of evaluation processes
- Transparency in the criteria for evaluating and selecting reviewers

3. Open Science Policies

Diamond OA publisher policies should align with Open Science and promote transparency, open access, and collaboration in research:

- Diamond OA publishers do not allow journals that ask authors for article processing charges (APCs).
- Authors retain copyright by publishing under licences such as Creative Commons (CC BY).
- Print-on-demand versions can be made available.
- Support is provided for unrestricted access to information, promoting rights retention and content reuse.
- Effective academic communication practices support indexing and deposit of works, boosting the visibility of papers.

4. Transparency and equity in editorial practices

The editorial policies of Diamond OA journals need to be clear and accessible to ensure the quality and credibility of research, aligning with international ethical standards:

- Transparency of editorial policies reinforces the integrity and quality of published research, increasing societal trust.
- The functions and responsibilities of the people who are involved in the editorial process – authors, editors, and reviewers – should be clearly described on the journal website.
- The evaluation criteria for selected articles refer to transparent and ethical standards, and include plagiarism detection protocols and techniques.
- Editorial policies should contribute to reducing inequalities in knowledge access: language, race, gender...
- Editorial policies should take into account criteria of equality, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB), for gender-balanced, and diverse editorial and review teams.

Tips:

- Make sure to adopt an international standard for interoperability and quality to ensure open and equitable access to content. Adopt systems that are based on open-source software for efficient knowledge distribution.
- Establish a review process that is both rigorous and transparent. Publish and share the evaluation criteria and processes used to select articles.
- Align your editorial policies with Open Science principles, promoting transparency, free access, and collaboration in research. Avoid charging for article processing and adopt publication under Creative Commons licences. Also, make print versions available on demand.
- Ensure transparency and fairness in editorial practices. Disclose the roles and responsibilities of the people involved in the editorial process, and ensure that evaluation criteria are transparent and ethical, including protocols for plagiarism detection. Implement policies that reduce inequalities in access to knowledge, including criteria of equality, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) in the composition of editorial and review teams.

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3) Implementing community-led governance in publishing services

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Introduction
<p>These guidelines on community-led governance in publishing services will help ensure coherence, transparency, and effectiveness in editorial management. Community-led governance of journal publishing services requires that clear processes, policies, and structures are put into place that regulate operations and decision-making across publications. Every aspect of how the journal is run, from the composition of the editorial team to peer review protocols and editorial ethics, must be explicitly defined and publicly accessible.</p> <p>The transparency of the editorial processes leading to the selection of articles is essential for ensuring a trusted relationship between all members of the scientific community who are involved in the journal: authors, reviewers, editors, and readers. A selection process that involves the participation of experts that are external to the editorial team can help ensure the objectivity of editorial decisions.</p> <p>In this context, the introduction of clear protocols and the dissemination of guidelines are necessary to promote the quality and consistency of publications.</p>
Body
<p>Governance refers to the set of processes, policies, and structures that regulate the functioning and decision-making uniformly across all publications in a journal. It is good practice to fully articulate the relationship between publishing services and the publications resulting from them.</p>

Governance. Publishing services:

Elements that Diamond OA publishers could consider:

1. Adopt procedures and guidelines about the composition and responsibilities of the editorial team, submission handling and selection processes (peer review), publication policies, editorial ethics, and transparency in content management.
2. Declare the journal's mission, objectives, and scope in a clearly structured and easily accessible way on their website.
3. Provide style sheets or guides that provide information about the desired presentation of submissions in a coherent and uniform manner.
3. Define protocols that formalize and make explicit how the different members of the scientific community – authors, editors, and reviewers – interact in decision-making.

These actions include:

- Publication identification: The publisher and its journals should put into place a mechanism that unambiguously establishes a recognized and identified link between the publisher and its journals.
 - Dissemination activities.
 - Training, evaluation, and monitoring.
 - Cooperation with other infrastructures. In the case of co-edition, establish a contractual relationship.
4. Ensure that all journals have transparent mechanisms for selecting the members of their respective governance bodies (such as advisory or editorial boards), based on their functions and responsibilities. Make these selection processes publicly available to ensure transparency of governance. It is good practice to have a detailed procedure for the duration of the positions, the required profiles, and the established time, when and how it is renewed: A public, detailed, and accessible protocol, reflecting and ensuring the degree of external decision-making in the publication of content.
 5. Establish and disseminate guidelines for proper publication planning in aspects related to bodies and decision-making:
 - Formalisation and explicitness of decision-making: who makes editorial decisions? How is consensus reached? Are there editorial meetings and what is their frequency? Make a clear distinction between journal-level and publisher-level policies, processes and decisions.
 - Provide a timetable specifying how often editorial policies are reviewed, and how new elements and changes are introduced in the editorial guidelines and practices.
 6. Ensure transparency and homogeneity in submission selection processes. All selection processes must follow general guidelines defined by the Diamond OA

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publisher, which can be complemented by more specific journal-level guidelines. Recommend that reviewers of submissions are sought outside of the editorial team and the Diamond OA publisher's institution.

7. Assessment processes: Consider alignment with international initiatives such as DORA and CoARA.

Tips:

- Establish clear protocols for decision-making at every level, from editorial team selection to the review and selection of submissions. This allows to clearly establish the interactions, roles and responsibilities of the various members of the scientific community – authors, editors, and reviewers – in decision-making. These protocols should also address the identification of publications, institutional relations, dissemination activities, training, monitoring, evaluation, and follow-up, as well as collaborating with other services, especially in co-publishing scenarios.
- Implement a detailed and transparent selection process for members of the editorial teams and boards, and clearly define their roles and responsibilities. This process should specify the duration of their appointment, the required profile, renewal procedures, and the selection protocol.
- When applicable, formalise editorial decision-making and planning with defined meeting frequencies.
- Make a clear distinction between journal-level and publisher-level policies, processes and decisions, and establish a schedule for periodic reviews of editorial policies.
- Recommend that reviewers of submissions are sought outside of the editorial team and the Diamond OA publisher's institution.

References

Further reading

- Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA): <https://sfdora.org/>
- Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA): <https://coara.eu>

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4) Copyright, authors' rights policy

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Introduction
<p>These guidelines provide a brief overview of basic concepts related to copyright. In addition, best practices in defining and displaying copyright policies for editors and publishers are described and explained.</p>
Body
<p>What is copyright or authors' rights?</p> <p>Different legal systems around the world use different words and legal provisions for the concept of moral and economic rights that authors have over the works they have created. Despite this variety, there are various basic commonalities that can be identified related to copyright (or authors' rights) in scholarly publishing. While copyright is regulated by the copyright acts of each country, some international agreements are in place (such as The Berne Convention, or the WIPO Copyright Treaty) that create a minimal common ground allowing for the same procedures to be applied globally.</p> <p>For publishers and editors in the scholarly publishing domain, it is important to understand the basics of copyright in order to be able to formulate appropriate copyright policies for their publications. These guidelines, however, are general in nature, and cannot account for all individual legal contexts. For all further clarifications, publishing services are advised to engage with a legal expert in their jurisdiction.</p> <p>Copyright is a subset of intellectual property rights. It refers to the rights of creators of literary, scholarly, and artistic works. It is important to mention that the copyright only protects the rights over expressions, but not over ideas, procedures, methods or concepts. Another important thing about copyright is that there needs to be no act of registering copyright in order for a work to be protected. The copyright automatically exists from the moment of the creation of the work.</p> <p>The author has moral and economic rights. Examples of a moral right include the right of attribution, i.e. the right to be acknowledged as the author of a work, and the right to oppose</p>

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changes to a work that could harm the creator's reputation. Examples of economic rights include the right to reproduce the work in any format, the right to communicate the work to the public (e.g. by making it available online), or the right to translation or adaptation of the work. While economic rights can be (and often are) transferred to others, fully or partially, moral rights are inalienable.

Economic rights are not eternal, they expire (in most legal systems) 70 years after the authors' death, when the work enters the public domain.

However, since copyright legislation is an effort to balance the interests of copyright holders and the public, there exist some limitations and exceptions to copyright, i.e. situations or purposes for which a copyrighted work can be used without asking for the permission of a copyright holder and without remunerating them. Those limitations and exceptions are typically provided in national laws on copyright, and usually include the use of work for the purposes of quotation, text and data mining for research purposes, for use by print-disabled people, or for other purposes. Such limitations and exceptions, sometimes referred to as "fair use" or "fair dealing" can differ across national regulations. This lack of harmonisation brings complexity and presents a barrier to the (re)use of copyrighted works. Diamond OA journals and publishers should strive to formulate clear policies that remove those uncertainties.

Who is the original copyright holder?

Different legal regimes have different rules for who is viewed as the original copyright holder. In some legal systems, the original copyright holder must always be a natural person (an author/the authors), and cannot be a legal person.

In other legal systems, there are special provisions related to "works for hire" which may apply to scholarly works, for instance by authors employed by academic institutions. This means that while the author(s) will always retain their moral rights to the work created, the economic rights can belong to the employer from the moment the work is created. Even in such situations, most academic institutions usually (informally or explicitly) leave decisions about copyright to the authors who can decide how and where to publish their works and who to transfer their copyright to.

The author can transfer their economic rights or give the exploitation right to others, either as an exclusive or non-exclusive right, or as a right that is unlimited or limited in terms of content, time or space.

Copyright in scholarly publishing

Traditional publishers of closed access journals and books used to require "copyright transfer" or the licence to publish that implied the exclusive and unlimited establishment of

the right of exploitation of the work. Such copyright transfers were only legally valid if they were established by an explicit (written) copyright agreement.

If there is no written contract, but the author submits the work and agrees to its publication, the publisher acquires only the right to publish, but not the right to further dispose of the author's work. In such cases, the author reserves the right to freely dispose of his work (e.g. the right to approve derivatives or commercial exploitation) and the author has the right to decide on the conditions of use of the work and on the licences.

This is why it is important that there is an agreement between the author and the publisher on granting an open licence (typically, one of Creative Commons licences) in some form, even when there is no written publishing contract (it could as well work as an online submission form). The publisher cannot subsequently grant a CC licence to the work without the knowledge and consent of the author.

Although in the absence of a written publishing contract, the authors 'retain the rights' to dispose of their work, it is preferable that this is not just a tacit practice, but that the publisher/journal makes its position on that matter clear and publicly available (in the form of a separate copyright policy or a part of an open access policy).

It is a good practice that all prospective authors have a chance to learn about the copyright policy of each journal they are considering for submissions.

Good practices for formulating copyright policies

All journals should define their copyright policies and make an explicit statement about the main issue, i.e. whether authors retain copyright or the publisher requires copyright transfer (or an exclusive licence to publish). For Diamond OA journals, it is always a good practice not to ask for copyright transfer.

Additionally, journals should make their position on open licences clear (as described in the Guidelines on open licensing).

If a publisher publishes several journals, it is preferable, but not necessary, that the copyright policies are aligned across all journals.

There are several places where information on copyright should be expressed:

- In the instructions to the authors
- On separate pages or sections of a journal / a publisher dedicated to copyright and/or open access
- In publishing contracts/agreements if they exist (regardless of what they are called: publication statements, publication permissions, licences to publish, copyright

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agreements...)

- By registering policies in the database [Sherpa Romeo](#)
- By recording policies in the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#)
- In the full text of the works/paper (stating who is the copyright holder)
- In the metadata description of the work (indicating who is the copyright holder), although this often depends on the capabilities of the platform

Important:

All the above-mentioned places should express the harmonized views of the journal. If the journal is available on multiple platforms, the information should be aligned across platforms.

Diamond OA journals should agree that the author(s) retain unlimited rights to exploit their work and decide on the terms of use of their work and that they certainly have the right to reuse their own work.

If a journal uses some other [CC licence](#) besides CC BY, it is very important to state who is the copyright holder, so that those who want to request permission for commercial use or adaptations and derivative use know who to contact. Stating that the copyright holders are both the publisher/journal and the authors is unclear and not helpful in such situations.

Alternative options?

The *Diamond Open Access Standard* (DOAS) strongly recommends authors' rights retention, but other options are possible as well.

OA journals can claim the exclusive right to exploit the work, or the right to exploit it for some purposes and in some ways (e.g. the right to decide on commercial uses or the right to adaptations).

DOAJ does not consider this a recommended practice but accepts such journals as well. In case the publisher has acquired the exclusive right to use the work, they can independently decide on licences and assign them to the published works. However, in combination with free licences (CC BY), such practice does not make much sense. Combined with more restrictive CC BY-NC/ND/NC-ND licence, this means that the journal decides and approves commercial use and adaptations, and even the authors themselves need to ask permission from the publisher.

Rights to reuse copyrighted works (Third party copyright)

If other people's works (or their parts) are used in the publication, it is necessary to obtain permission for use. The responsibility for obtaining permission rests with the author, but the journal or publishing service should:

- Warn about it in the instructions to the authors (indicate what kind of permission should be obtained: usually non-exclusive, but unlimited)
- Ask for a guarantee in the author's statement that permissions have been obtained.
- Check whether all sources are properly cited in the article

If necessary, state the terms of use (the third-party work's licence) separately for individual elements in the work

Tips

- Create clear, concise and precise policies, so that authors don't feel insecure about their rights.
- If authors retain copyright, and the publisher acquires only the right to publish, the author reserves the right to freely dispose of their work (e.g. the right to approve derivatives or commercial exploitation) and the author has the right to decide on the conditions of use of the work and on the licences. This is why it is important that there is an agreement between the author and the publisher on granting an open licence.
- For Diamond OA journals it is always a good practice not to ask for copyright transfer.
- Information on copyright should be stated in several places and all given information should be aligned and regularly updated.
- Journals need to guide authors in obtaining permission for the reuse of third-party copyrighted materials.
- Journals and publishing providers should ensure that copyright information (including open licences) are provided in human- and machine-readable form (via metadata).

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WIPO World Intellectual Property Organisation. <i>Copyright</i>. https://www.wipo.int/copyright/en/index.html <p>Labastida i Juan, I., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Proudman, V., Treadway, J. (2023). <i>Opening Knowledge: Retaining Rights and Open Licensing in Europe</i>. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8084051</p>
Further reading
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5) Use of open licences in open access publishing

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Introduction
<p>These guidelines provide support for IPSPs in the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing content under an open licence (preferably CC BY) to ensure further reuse without restrictions • Providing clear information to any user of the published content on the conditions of

(re)use, in human and machine-readable form, on the article/chapter and publication level

- Providing clear information on the IPSP's policy towards authors' rights, copyright and licensing
- Accurate reporting and regular updating of the information in relevant registries (such as [DOAJ](#) or [Sherpa Romeo](#)) by journal publishers

Body

The Open Science framework emphasises two important elements of Open Access (OA) publishing related to copyright and terms of use. The first is that authors (or their institutions) should retain rights to their scholarly outputs. The second is that all scholarly works should be made openly available directly at the time of publication and reusable under the terms of an open licence so that content is truly open, and knowledge is available to be both used and reused (Labastida i Juan et al., 2023).

Regulating the use of published content

The use of all published works, unless otherwise specified, is fully defined by legal regulations on copyright in the respective country. Legal regulations on copyright are today largely harmonised around the world, and while copyright laws generally allow for the use of copyrighted works by the public for some purposes without asking for permission, these limitations to copyright do not grant to the public the right of full reuse of a work. Therefore the publication under the default regime of all rights reserved does not allow for the full reuse of a work so that all the benefits of open access can be realised.

If OA journals wish their content to be truly open for different kinds of use and reuse, by all users, and without the need to seek permissions, they can do so by granting such permissions in advance, clearly and publicly. Granting such liberal permissions in advance is best achieved by using standardised and machine-readable open licences. In the world of scholarly publishing, various types of open licences can be adopted, but the Creative Commons set of licences are currently the most often used in both policy and practice, and have become the *de facto* standard for this purpose (Creative Commons, 2019). To the user, the licences provide a clear answer to the question "What can I do with this work?" by granting rights under certain conditions. Rights and conditions are described by the following elements:

- The work can be used freely so long as attribution is given to the author, the copyright holder and any party that it is stated to be acknowledged (BY - attribution)
- The work can be used exclusively for non-commercial purposes (NC - non-commercial)
- The work can be used freely but the creation and dissemination of derivative works is not allowed (ND - non-derivatives)
- The work can be used freely but any derivative work must be licenced under the same

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licence or an equivalent licence (SA - share alike)

These conditions can be combined, and their combinations give rise to six different licences: CC BY (the most liberal one), CC BY-SA, CC BY-NC, CC BY-NC-SA, CC BY-ND and CC BY-NC-ND (the most restrictive one).

The definition of Open Access as set out in the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI, 2002) and in the Berlin Declaration (MPG, 2003) is to grant full reuse of published academic outputs, subject to proper attribution of authorship. This definition entails that CC BY is the preferred licence to be applied to scholarly works. For OA journals (and for the authors of their content), a CC BY licence brings clear benefits and advantages. It enables full reuse and application without barriers in different contexts: research, innovation, education, culture, and business. It enhances the impact of published works, both academic and societal. At the same time, it provides legal protection for authors and rights holders, as the condition of attribution always applies. In the domain of journal publishing, attribution means that the original authors and original publication should always be cited and linked, ideally by using persistent identifiers. For book publishing, the question of selecting a licence is a more complex one, see the section “Discipline- and format-specific considerations on licences” for a more detailed differentiation.

Open licences in practice

While CC BY is clearly the recommended licence for OA journals, the ultimate choice of licence for each journal should be a result of thoughtful consideration, and all stakeholders (editors, owners, publishers, authors and reviewers) should be made fully aware of the implications of the licence chosen.

It is possible to decide that only one licence will be used for all journal content (or even for all of the journals of one publisher), but in some cases, journals can opt for the adoption of several licences and leave the decision on a licence to the authors of each article.

Various factors can influence the journal's decision on a specific/recommended licence:

- Traditions and culture in a specific scientific discipline (e.g. some fields of humanities are reluctant to implement licences that permit derivative works since they prefer to control the rights to translations, for example)
- Research funder requirements (e.g. some European and international funders require CC BY for grantees)
- Requirements of some databases (e.g. DOAJ requests that the journal uses any one of the CC licences, while it must permit the use of a Creative Commons licence that allows the creation of derivative products in order to obtain the DOAJ Seal)

A journal may impose different types of licences for different versions of a manuscript

(preprint/postprint/final version). However, this is not recommended for Diamond OA journals. OA journals should ideally leave it to the authors to decide under the terms of which licence they will distribute the preprint or the author-accepted manuscript versions.

When a journal decides on the licence that will be used, it needs to both make sure that the licence is actually assigned to the published content and that the content is distributed under the terms of that licence.

Depending on who the holder of the copyright is (or who has the exclusive right to publish the work), the assignation of licences has 2 routes:

- A - If the author has retained the rights (which is the recommended practice for OA journals), the author should choose or approve the licence (via contract, statement or during the online application)
- B - If the publisher is the holder of exclusive rights, they can determine the licence independently.

For either route, a journal's decision at one point in time to use a certain licence does not automatically mean that this licence applies to all works of the journal prior to that decision. A journal that allows authors to retain their rights (situation A) would have to obtain permissions from authors (right holders) to apply licences to older content, while a journal that is a holder of exclusive rights (situation B) could decide on its own to apply open licences to backfile content.

Good practices highlighting licensing policies and the licences themselves

It is very important that the terms of use expressed through the open licences are communicated and stated very clearly, at different places, at different levels of granularity and in different ways.

- Licence usage policies should be stated:
 - In the instructions to the authors
 - On separate pages/sections dedicated to copyright and/or open access
 - In publishing contracts or agreements, if they exist
 - By registering policies in the Sherpa Romeo database
 - By registering the journal policies in DOAJ
 - On the journal pages of the publishing service's platform of choice, or on a book publisher's website
- The licences themselves are displayed:
 - In the articles/chapters themselves, in all formats of the complete text (e.g. PDF and HTML), machine-readable (as a URL linking to the deed of the licence, the human-readable version of the legal text) and human-readable
 - In the metadata description of the works
 - They should be displayed through icons, hyperlinks to the deed of the licence

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<p>or the full legal text of the licence and the short descriptive text in the article</p>
<p>Important tips:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ All places where the journal copyright and licencing policies are described should express the harmonised views of the journal or publisher. ○ If journals are available on multiple platforms the information should be consistent across platforms. ○ licence terms and copyright policy should be used with consent and not contradict each other. If a journal revises its copyright policy, care should be taken that it is still aligned with the licensing terms of individual articles. ○ Besides displaying the licence, it is also necessary that the rights holder is stated clearly (In case of more restrictive licences, those who want to request permission for commercial use or derivatives should be able to identify who they need to contact)
<p>Discipline- and format-specific considerations on licences</p> <p>In some scholarly fields, the use of so-called “third-party copyright” (materials for which other persons or institutions are authors, owners and rights-holders) is more common than in others, such as, for instance, in art history. Where that is the case, journals should give detailed advice to authors on how to acquire permission to use such materials for them to be able to insert them into their own works and distribute them under the open licence. When it is not possible, such third-party materials should be clearly labelled to communicate that they are not being distributed under the same licence as the rest of the work. In some cases, it can even be required that such materials be omitted from the OA editions (Hudson & Aplin, 2023)</p> <p>While it is generally agreed that CC BY is the best choice for scholarly journals, there isn’t yet such an agreement with regard to scholarly books that is particularly relevant to the disciplines where long-form texts are the dominant publishing model. There are different considerations on the preferred licences for books (Collins et al., 2013; Adema et al., 2021), and some negative experiences with the most liberal licences.</p>
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6) Research data sharing policy

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Xenia van Edig, Laura Rincón
Introduction
<p>These guidelines help Diamond OA publishers and service providers implement a research data sharing policy, recognising the essential role of the availability of the article's underlying research data in supporting conclusions and reproducibility.</p> <p>It's a good practice to make data available to editors and reviewers during the manuscript review process and, if possible, make it available to everyone by the time of publication in a FAIR manner through repositories, providing persistent identifiers (PIDs) and linking from the publication to the research data and from the research data to the publication.</p>
Body
<p>Re-use our model wording below to develop your research data sharing policy:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px;"> <p><i>[A journal/ publisher] encourages/requires [select your preferred option] authors to share research data that are needed to confirm the results published in the manuscript and/or enhance the published manuscript under the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. We encourage authors to share supporting software applications, high-resolution images, background datasets, sound or video clips, large appendices, data tables and other relevant items that cannot be included in the article.</i></p> <p>Authors may deposit relevant data in a FAIR-compliant repository – institutional, disciplinary, or general-purpose (e.g. Zenodo). Assistance in finding a FAIR compliant repository can be found here: https://repositoryfinder.datacite.org/ and https://www.re3data.org/. Authors should also provide via the repository any information needed to replicate, validate, and/or reuse the results / their study and analysis of the research data. This includes details of any software, instruments and other tools used to process the results. Where possible, the tools and instruments themselves should also be provided. A DOI will be assigned to each research data file, enabling the research data to be</p> </div>

cited the same way as publications. Authors affirm that data protection regulations, ethical standards, third party copyright and other rights have been respected in the process of collecting, processing and sharing data.

Exceptions: We recognize that open sharing of data may not always be feasible. Exceptions to open access to research data underlying publications include the following: obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, the obligation to protect personal data and other legitimate constraints. Where open access is not provided to the data needed to validate the conclusions of a publication that reports original results, authors should make metadata available explaining the research and access rules to the data.

If data access is restricted for ethical or security reasons, the manuscript must include:

- a description of the restrictions on the data;
- what, if anything, the relevant Institutional Review Board (IRB) or equivalent said about the data sharing; and
- all necessary information required for a reader or reviewer to apply for access to the data and the conditions under which access will be granted.

In instances where the data cannot be made available, the manuscript must include:

- an explanation of the data protection concern;
- any intermediary data that can be de-identified without compromising anonymity;
- what, if anything, the relevant IRB or equivalent said about data sharing; and
- where applicable, all necessary information required for a reader or peer reviewer to apply for access to the data and the conditions under which access will be granted.

Tips:

- Special attention should be paid to data protection issues, specifically around GDPR and / or other national or regional data protection policies (See more in GDPR and Personal data section). Where human data cannot be effectively de-identified, data must not be shared in order to protect participant privacy, unless the individuals have given explicit written consent that their identifiable data can be made publicly available.
- Research data should be linked from a Data Accessibility Statement within the submitted paper, which will be made public upon publication. A 'Data Accessibility Statement' should be added to the submission, prior to the reference list, providing the details of the data accessibility, including the DOI linking to it. If the data is restricted in any way and/or is not being made available within the journal publication, a statement from the author should be provided to explain why.

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- The open research data must be deposited under an open license that permits unrestricted access (e.g., CC0, CC BY). More restrictive licenses should only be used if there is a valid reason to do so (e.g., legal).
- Authors should be asked to
 - Check whether the repository where the research data is deposited has a sustainability model. The journal can indicate preferred repositories.
 - Provide a version of the deposited data in an open, non-proprietary format.
 - Describe the deposited data in such a way that a third party can make sense of it (e.g., sensible column headers, descriptions in a readme text file).
 - When citing or making claims based on data, provide the reference to data in the same way as they cite publications. We recommend the format proposed by [the FORCE11 Data Citation Principles](#).

Discipline-specific considerations

Research involving human subjects, human material, or human data, must have been performed in accordance with the [Declaration of Helsinki](#). Where applicable, the studies must have been approved by an appropriate Ethics Committee. The identity of the research subject should be anonymized whenever possible. For research involving human subjects, informed consent (or other legal grounds, e.g. from [GDPR, Article 6](#)) to participate in the study must be obtained from participants (or their legal guardian).

References

- Datacite. Repository Finder. <https://commons.datacite.org/repositories>
- FORCE 11. *Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles*. <https://force11.org/info/joint-declaration-of-data-citation-principles-final/>
- FORCE 11. *The FAIR data principles*. <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>
- European Commission. *General Data protection Regulation. Article 6 'Lawfulness of processing'*. <https://gdpr.eu/tag/gdpr/>
- Re3Data <https://www.re3data.org/>
- World Medical Association. *Declaration of Helsinki*. <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects>
- Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>

Further reading

- COPE. *Data and Reproducibility*. <https://publicationethics.org/data>
- GLOSSA Journal Policies: <https://www.glossa-journal.org/site/journal-policies>
- Hrynaszkiewicz, I., Simons, N., Hussain, A., Grant, R., Goudie, S. (2020). 'Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers'. *Data Science Journal* 19 (1): 5. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-005>
- Open Research Europe. *Policies*. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/about/policies>

- Open Research Europe. *Open Data, Software and Code Guidelines*. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines>

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7) Preprints

Lead author(s)
Iryna Kuchma
Contributor(s)
Peer reviewer(s)
Elio Pellin, Laura Rincón
Introduction
It's a good practice to accept the submission of unreviewed and peer-reviewed preprints that are already available on preprint servers or in open repositories and include this in your policy. Authors should also be allowed to disseminate their preprint version(s) at any time before and after article acceptance and publishing.
Body
<p>Preprints are scientific manuscripts that are publicly shared prior to peer-review and journal publication via preprint platforms. An increasing number of journals accept sharing of preprints prior to publication. Early and open sharing is a part of transparent research practices and one of the measures to increase reproducibility of research outputs.</p> <p>Examples of preprint servers/repositories: Zenodo – multidisciplinary; ArXiv – physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics; bioRxiv – life sciences; medRxiv – medicine and health sciences; SocArXiv – social sciences and humanities; PsyArxiv – behavioural sciences; LawArXiv – law; MediArXiv – media and communication studies; Knowledge Commons (formerly Humanities Commons). Use the Directory of Open Access Preprint Repositories to find more, please browse by disciplines).</p>

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Tips:

Diamond OA journals and publishers should include a note in their 'Author's responsibilities/guidelines' clauses that posting of preprints on preprint servers or repositories is not considered prior publication. Authors should be allowed to submit articles accompanied by the reviews provided by a preprint peer review platform such as [PCI](#). Authors should be asked to disclose details of preprint posting upon submission of the manuscript. This must include a link to the location of the preprint. Note that full double-blind review is not an option for a journal when preprints are allowed, because it is impossible to ensure the anonymity of authors. Should the submission be published, the authors are expected to update the information associated with the preprint version on the preprint server/repository to show that a final version has been published in the journal, including the DOI linking directly to the publication. Authors should be allowed to disseminate their preprint version(s) at any time before and after article acceptance and publishing.

References

- Arxiv <https://arxiv.org/>
- BioRxiv <https://www.biorxiv.org/>
- Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe (CCSD). <https://www.ccsd.cnrs.fr/en/>
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR). <https://www.coar-repositories.org/>
- Directory of Open Access Preprint Repositories. <https://doapr.coar-repositories.org/>
- Knowledge Commons <https://hcommons.org/core/>
- LawArxiv <https://osf.io/preprints/lawarxiv>
- medRxiv <https://www.medrxiv.org/>
- Peer Community In (PCI) <https://peercommunityin.org>.
- PsyRxiv <https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv>
- SocArxiv <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv>
- Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>

Further reading

- European Commission. *Horizon Europe Programme Guide*, Version 4.0, 15 October 2023 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
- Preprint resource center: *FAQs, policies, and materials*. <https://asapbio.org/preprint-info>
- Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12179619>

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8) Self-archiving policy

Lead author(s)
Iryna Kuchma
Contributor(s)
Iva Melinščak Zlodi
Peer reviewer(s)
Laura Rincón
Introduction
Your self-archiving policy should allow dissemination of the article preprint version at any time, the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) after acceptance, and/or the Version of Record (VoR) after publication in a repository of the authors' choice.
Body
<p>Self-archiving refers to the act of authors depositing a free copy of an electronic document in a repository/archive in order to provide open access to it. The term often refers to the self-archiving of peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers, as well as theses and dissertations, book chapters, and other research outputs in the author's institutional repository or disciplinary or general purpose repository (e.g. Zenodo) for the purpose of maximizing availability, visibility, usage, and citation impact (Self-archiving, OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit). Repositories are digital platforms that hold research output and provide free, immediate and permanent access to research results for anyone to use, download and share (Repository (open access repository), OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit).</p> <p>Diamond OA journals and publishers should encourage rather than prevent the free circulation of knowledge and accept the submissions of preprints that are already available. They should allow the deposit of any version of the published work in open repositories of authors' choice, before or after the publication. If the journal or publisher uses a CC BY license, and/or if they have a policy allowing authors to retain publishing rights, the right to deposit and share is already granted to the authors.</p> <p>Diamond OA journals and publishers can re-use the model wording below to develop their self-archiving policy:</p>
<p>Authors can deposit preprints (versions before peer review) at any time, Author Accepted Manuscripts (AAMs) after acceptance, and/or Versions of Record (VoRs) after publication in</p>

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a repository of the authors' choice (e.g. an institutional, disciplinary and general-purpose repository. etc.).

Full bibliographic information (authors, article title, journal title, volume, issue, pages) about the original publication must be provided and links must be made to the article's DOI and the license.

Tips:

- Diamond OA journals and publishers could let authors decide on the license used when depositing their content, or recommend their preferred license.
- Authors should be recommended or required to deposit all supplementary materials (e.g. research data), and provide links between those deposits.
- Authors should be reminded to update the records of previously deposited versions with links to newer versions.
- Authors should be informed that sharing through academic networks and social media is not equal to the benefits of repositories. Repositories are usually non-profits, open and interoperable and ensure long-term preservation and access. See more details here: [A social networking site is not an open access repository](#).

References

- OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit. *Self- archiving* <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/glossary/article/3681612-self-archiving>
- OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit. *Repository* <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/glossary/article/1519672-repository-open-access-repository>
- University Of California, Office of Scholarly Communication. *A social networking site is not an open access repository* <https://osc.universityofcalifornia.edu/2015/12/a-social-networking-site-is-not-an-open-access-repository/>

Further reading

- Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12179619>

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9) Handling negative research results

Lead author(s)
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Contributor(s)
Peer reviewer(s)
Elio Pellin, Laura Rincón
Introduction
<p>These guidelines outline a publisher-level policy regarding the publication of negative or unexpected scientific results and data.</p>
Body
<p>The <i>Diamond Open Access Standard's</i> (DOAS) guidelines recommend that Institutional Publishers (IPs) acknowledge as a matter of publisher policy that the publication of negative or unexpected scientific results and data that do not confirm the initial hypotheses and experimental designs of the authors, contribute to the advancement of science and scholarship.</p> <p>Typically, journals and editors tend to privilege positive and original results, which leads to the 'reproducibility crisis': many, if not most, studies cannot be reproduced. As a result, it is important for publishers and journals to correct this bias towards positive results, and pay particular attention to replication studies showing that a given result cannot in fact be reproduced, demonstrating that the initial hypothesis is falsified.</p> <p>IPs should make the editorial teams of their journals aware of this bias and of their publisher-level policy regarding the publication of negative or unexpected scientific results and data.</p>
Discipline-specific considerations
<p>A publication policy encouraging the publication of negative results is mostly relevant for those (sub)disciplines that are concerned with testing hypotheses on the basis of data. Many disciplines in the humanities engage in research and scholarship that do not typically adopt this research process, from philosophy to comparative literature and critical editions. At the same time, it is important not to exclude the Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines too quickly from the publication of negative results. Historical research in archives, for instance, could also lead to interesting negative results that scholars in the field may wish to be aware of.</p>

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS). Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12179619
Further reading
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bik, Elisabeth M. (2024). 'Publishing negative results is good for science Open Access'. <i>Access Microbiology</i>, 6.4, https://doi.org/10.1099/acmi.0.000792 • Enago Academy. (2021). <i>Why should negative results be published?</i> • https://www.enago.com/academy/why-should-negative-results-be-published/ • Nimpf, Simon & David A. Keays. (2020). 'Why (and how) we should publish negative data'. <i>EMBO Reports</i> 21, https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6945059/ • Popper, Karl. 1959. <i>The logic of scientific discovery</i>. Abingdon-on-Thames: Routledge.
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10) Availability of research protocols, methods and software

Lead author(s)
Iryna Kuchma
Contributor(s)
Peer reviewer(s)
Michelle Barker, Xenia van Edig
Introduction
<p>It's a good open science practice to include requirements on the availability of research protocols and methods in Diamond OA journal policies. Diamond OA journals and publishers should encourage authors to share them in public repositories and to use persistent identifiers for making the relevant connections between articles and other research outputs. This will make it easier to replicate and build on published work.</p>

To facilitate reproducibility and FAIRification of research, Diamond OA journals and publishers should consider encouraging the use of free/open source software. Diamond OA journals and publishers should define a policy on the availability of research software and ask authors for a statement of software availability.

Body

A Research Protocol is a detailed document prepared before conducting a study, often written as part of ethics and funding applications, that includes information relating to the background, rationale and aims of the study, as well as the hypotheses which reflect the researchers' expectations, and a "recipe" for conducting the study, including methodological details and clear analysis plans ([FORRT - Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training Glossary](#)).

Research protocols are publicly shared to attract new collaborators or facilitate efficient collaboration across labs (e.g. <https://www.protocols.io/>). In medical and educational fields, protocols are often a separate article type suitable for publication in journals.

Availability of software, its acknowledgement and citation

"Some of the most important scientific breakthroughs of the last decade, such as the solution for the [protein structure prediction problem](#), were made possible because of the availability of rich and comprehensive data sources and [powerful software tools](#) for data representation and analysis, numerical computation, and modeling." (Chan Zuckerberg Initiative Science, 2022). Nevertheless, software is generally not formally cited in scientific publications. At best it is either mentioned in the methods section of an article, or it may be identified through the dependencies of research code deposited by the authors. "Software is a critical part of modern research and yet there is little support across the scholarly ecosystem for its acknowledgement and citation." (Smith et al, 2016).

Software availability is essential for scientific reproducibility – the ability to replicate published findings by running the same computational tool on data generated by the study (Brito et al, 2020)). In addition, there is a correlation between the use of free and open-source software, software citation and article retractions. Errors in processing data and computation of results, software errors or misuse are common reasons for scientific self-correction and article retractions. The study found that "retracted articles use less free and open-source software, hampering reproducible research and quality control. Moreover, such differences are also present concerning software citation, where retracted articles less frequently follow software citation guidelines regarding free and open-source software." (Schindler et al., 2023).

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Measures to ensure the reproducibility of results

Diamond OA journals and publishers can enhance the reproducibility of research outputs by encouraging Open Access to research software, workflows, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows, electronic notebooks and others - needed for the re-use or validation of the article's conclusions and the validation and reuse of research data. "Reproducibility of some or all results is important as it increases the performance of research and innovation (wider use of research results); it limits waste of resources (less duplication and fewer false baselines); it increases the quality and the reliability of research (stronger methods, controls and reporting); and, as a result, it may increase the trust of citizens in science." ([Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#))

Tips:

- Diamond OA journals' and publishers' guidelines for authors should ask them to specify how they will ensure robust statistical analysis that can be repeated (power of sample, robust experimental techniques, open software, ...) and make provisions to validate, demonstrate, make interoperable, scale-up and overall make replicable the results of their R&I activities. Authors should be asked to provide information about the research outputs/tools/instruments needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications or to validate/re-use research data.
- Diamond OA journals and publishers should consider including the following Reporting standards paragraph in their journal policies: "[*Journal title*] is committed to serving the research community by ensuring that all articles include enough information to allow others to reproduce the work. A submitted manuscript should contain sufficient detail and references to permit reviewers and, subsequently, readers to verify the claims presented in it - e.g. provide complete details of the methods used, including time frames, etc. Authors are required to review the standards available for many research applications from [Equator Network](#) and use those that are relevant for the reported research applications. The deliberate presentation of false claims is a violation of ethical standards."
- Where applicable, authors should be asked to deposit step-by-step descriptions of their protocols on [protocols.io](#) and to include the persistent DOI in the Methods section of the manuscript.
- Where applicable, authors should be asked to upload their scientific code / scripts / models openly in a code repository.
- Diamond OA journals and publishers should consider software a legitimate and citable product of research. Software citations should be required in the same way as citations of other research products, such as publications and data: authors should be asked to include them in the reference list of a journal article.

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- [TOP guidelines](#) (Transparency and Openness Promotion) include eight modular standards: 1) Citation standards, 2) Data transparency, 3) Analytic methods (code) transparency, 4) Research materials transparency, 5) Design and analysis transparency, 6) Study preregistration, 7) Analysis plan preregistration, and 8) Replication, each with three levels of increasing stringency: Disclosure – the article must disclose whether or not materials are available; Requirement – the article must share materials when possible; Verification – third party must verify that the standard is being met. Diamond OA journals and publishers should select which of the eight transparency standards they wish to implement for transparency and reproducibility in published research and select a level of implementation for each. These features provide flexibility for adoption depending on disciplinary variation, but simultaneously establish community standards. Journal and publisher policies can be evaluated based on the degree to which they comply with the TOP Guidelines – TOP factor, which is a metric that reports the steps that a journal or publisher is taking to implement open science practices.

References

- Brito, J., Li, J., Moore, J., Greene, C., Nogoy, N., Garmire, L., Mangul, S. (2020). 'Recommendations to enhance rigor and reproducibility in biomedical research'. *GigaScience*, Volume 9, Issue 6, g1aa056, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/g1aa056>
- Chan Zuckerberg Initiative Science. (2022). *New data reveals the hidden impact of open source in science*. <https://medium.com/czi-technology/new-data-reveals-the-hidden-impact-of-open-source-in-science-11cc4a16fea2>
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- Smith A.M., Katz D.S., Niemeyer K.E., FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. (2016). Software citation principles. *PeerJ Computer Science* 2:e86 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.86>
- TOP Guidelines <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/top-guidelines>

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Further reading
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS). Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12179619 • PLOS. <i>Published peer-reviewed protocols</i>. https://plos.org/protocols • PLOS. <i>Open Methods</i>. https://plos.org/open-science/open-methods • PLOS. <i>Open Code</i>. https://plos.org/open-science/open-code
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11) Basic editorial information that should be displayed

Lead author(s)
Claire Redhead
Contributor(s)
Judith Barnsby
Peer reviewer(s)
Elio Pellin, Laura Rincón, Tobias Steiner
Introduction
<p>It is important that the website of a Diamond OA publisher provides clear and well-structured information for authors, readers and any other users, and that details on key elements are easy to find and understand. Diamond OA publishers should make sure that they carefully think about all relevant sections of information and ensure this is comprehensive on their website.</p>
Body
<p>The Diamond OA publisher’s website must provide a clear mission for the publication, outlining its aims and scope, and its target readership. Diamond OA publishers should indicate the frequency of issues, or state that the journal is published on a continuous basis. Publication dates quoted must be the actual dates that the publication became available online.</p> <p>Diamond OA publishers and journals should state explicitly that no mandatory fees are charged to authors. Some journals may choose to suggest a Voluntary Author Contribution</p>

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(VAC) whereby authors with access to institutional funding for open access publishing are given the opportunity to support the journal. It must be clear that there is no obligation to do so. For an example see the journal [Glossa Psycholinguistics' policy on VACs](#), or [that of the Open Library of Humanities](#).

Author guidelines must be available giving details of the submission process, including the languages in which manuscripts can be submitted, article types accepted, and any formatting requirements, stylesheets, or templates to be used.

Diamond OA publishers and journals must provide information about the evaluation procedure undertaken by the journal, including the expected timeframe for the process, who is involved at what stage of the process, how decisions are made and by whom. All submitted articles should undergo a rigorous evaluation process that adheres to best practices in scholarly publishing, and any specific practices followed in the relevant discipline. Evaluation may take place before or after publication, depending on the review model adopted by the Diamond OA publisher or journal.

The Diamond OA publisher's and journal's website should include a range of editorial policies that are easy to find and clearly describe aspects such as authorship and contributorship, how complaints and appeals regarding allegations of research misconduct will be handled and what the policy is for conflicts of interest. Following industry-standard practices is recommended, such as those provided by [COPE](#) (Committee on Publication Ethics).

Diamond OA publishers and journals should also feature policies on their website that address issues such as: text and data mining; whether or not authors can make the content available via open repositories and sharing services; and the archiving and presentation policy for published content. Diamond OA publishers and journals should clearly describe how any publishing infrastructure is maintained, backed up and protected from viruses and malware, as well as providing user instructions and documentation for editorial staff.

Tips:

- Information should be written clearly and be jargon free
- Details of all policies and procedures should be fully described and transparent
- Information should be easy to find by including it in relevant menus and cross linking between sections
- Getting external help reviewing a website can be useful and help identify areas where transparency could be improved

References

- COPE, DOAJ, OASPA, WAME. (2022). *Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing*. <https://publicationethics.org/sites/default/files/principles-transparency-best-practice-scholarly-publishing.pdf>

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Committee on Publication Ethics. <i>COPE Core Practices</i>. https://publicationethics.org/core-practices
Further reading
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Access Journals Toolkit. https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org Directory of Open Access Journals. <i>DOAJ Guide to Applying</i>. https://doaj.org/apply/guide/ Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association. <i>OASPA Membership Criteria</i>. https://www.oaspa.org/apply/membership-criteria/ JASPER Preservation Service. https://doaj.org/preservation/
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12) GDPR and Personal data

Lead author(s)
Clara Armengou
Contributor(s)
Dominic Mitchell
Peer reviewer(s)
Elio Pellin, Laura Rincón, Tobias Steiner
Introduction
These guidelines explain how IPSPs should handle personal information and comply with relevant regulations.
Body
<p>The GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) aims to ensure transparency and inform the public – the users, workers, team members etc of the Diamond OA publication service – about how your organisation uses, stores, and processes their personal data.</p> <p>If Diamond OA publishers and service providers handle the personal information of people within the EU, they must comply with GDPR and they must have a privacy notice that explains how they do that.</p>

Easy to read and understand

A privacy notice, a key requirement of the GDPR, is a public document that outlines how an organisation processes personal data. [Articles 12, 13](#), and [14](#) of the GDPR provide guidance on creating these notices, emphasising *clarity and accessibility*. Privacy notices must be *concise, transparent, clear, and accessible*. They should be in *plain language*, delivered promptly, and provided free of charge.

Tips for writing a clear and easy to understand privacy notice:

- Avoid vague qualifiers like 'may', 'might', 'sometimes', 'often'. Use 'will' and 'always' instead.
- Write in active tense with well-structured sentences.
- Use a spelling and grammar checker to help you keep sentences short and clear.
- Provide clear, specific explanations, e.g. instead of 'We will retain your personal details' write 'We will retain your name, email address and institution name.'

What's required

The specific information required in a privacy notice depends on whether the data is collected *directly from individuals* or *is received indirectly* from a third party.

When your organisation collects data directly, the notice must include:

- The organisation's identity, contact details, and those of its Data Protection Officer, if there is one, or the individual responsible for monitoring and implementing the guidelines of the GDPR).
- Purpose and legal basis for data processing.
- Legitimate interests of the organisation or third party.
- Recipients or categories of recipients.
- Details of any data transfers to third countries.
- Retention period or criteria for determining it.
- Details of the data subject's rights.
- Right to withdraw consent and
- Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.
- Whether the provision of personal data is part of a statutory or contractual requirement or obligation and the possible consequences of failing to provide the personal data
- Automated decision-making systems, including profiling.
- If data is obtained indirectly, the notice must also specify the categories of data obtained.

For example:

When your organisation obtains personal data indirectly (via another organization or service), your privacy notice must provide all the same information as above, except for:

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- Whether the provision of personal data is part of a statutory or contractual requirement or obligation and the possible consequences of failing to provide the personal data

And must include:

- The categories of personal data obtained

For example:

If Diamond OA publishers and service providers obtain personal data from a third party, they have to let the data subject know either:

- within one month of obtaining the data,
- upon first communication, or
- before sharing the data with another organization

How and where to inform individuals

Organizations should provide privacy notices in writing and electronically, making them accessible on their websites under the title “Privacy Policy” with a direct link from each page. Notices should also be available orally upon request via the Data Protection Officer.

Best practices

The EU website for GDPR offers a section on best practices for writing a compliant privacy notice: <https://gdpr.eu/privacy-notice/>, including a template for a privacy policy.

References

- European Commission. *General Data protection Regulation*. <https://gdpr.eu/tag/gdpr/>
- European Commission. *Writing a GDPR-compliant privacy notice* (template included) <https://gdpr.eu/privacy-notice/>

Further reading

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13) Choosing a platform

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Introduction
<p>These guidelines help Diamond OA publishers and journals understand what they need and what factors to take into account when choosing a platform for their journal(s). Choosing a proper journal management system and having a proper hosting arrangement will help Diamond OA publishers and journals meet the <i>Diamond Open Access Standard's</i> (DOAS) requirements.</p>
Body
<p>According to the <i>Diamond Open Access Standard</i> (DOAS), an online publishing platform should make it possible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for authors to submit their manuscripts using an online submission system, rather than sending it via email. Authors should be able to register an account, log in, fill out the required forms and attach the manuscript and other supporting materials. After the submission, they should be able to track the progress of their manuscript and communicate with the editor via the system. • for editors and editorial staff to communicate with authors, peer reviewers, editorial assistants, copyeditors, etc. via the system and to save all the correspondence in it. • to publish (display publicly on web pages) the metadata and full text of the articles accepted for publication. <p>As a minimum, the platform should have a clear interface usable by everyone, including those with disabilities and impairments, and adjustable to various screen sizes (responsive). Metadata should be available in both human and machine-readable formats and it is also recommended to expose machine-readable metadata via standard metadata exchange protocols and enable metadata export. The platform must comply with the security standards established by law and it must be maintained, updated, regularly backed up and protected against security threats.</p> <p>When choosing a platform for their journals, publishers should consider a number of factors and make some decisions.</p>

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

Choosing software for the journal platform

Use journal management software

The above-mentioned requirements can be difficult and costly to meet if a publishing platform has to be built from scratch or when trying to adjust a ready-made content management system that does not natively support scholarly publishing workflows (e.g. Wordpress, Drupal, Joomla, etc.). Most journal management software solutions, both proprietary and free and open source (FOSS), support these features out of the box.

Use free and open source software (FOSS)

Using a FOSS solution (e.g. [Open Journal Systems](#), [Janeway](#), [Kotahi](#), [PubSweet](#), etc.) is highly recommended because it is more cost-effective and software can be customised without having to pay or ask permission from the software producer.

Consider the following when deciding which software to use:

- What features do you need/want?
- Is the software properly documented and regularly updated?
- How large and active is the community behind it?
- Familiarise yourself with the functionalities offered by each solution (through software demos, video tutorials and documentation, the websites of the journal already using a particular software)
- Is integration with other technical infrastructures such as persistent identifiers providers (e.g. [Crossref](#) or [DataCite](#), [ORCID](#), [Research Organization Registry](#)) or long-term preservation services supported?
- Would it be possible to migrate the journal to a different software if needed (e.g. OJS to Janeway)?

Choosing a hosting option

Building an independent journal platform

In this scenario, software is downloaded from the software provider's website and installed on a server, which can be owned by the journal(s) owner or outsourced from a hosting provider. The journal owner is responsible for software updates and maintenance and sometimes also for backups and security.

Advantages

- Full control of the publishing platform and content
- High potential for customisation

Disadvantages

- Engagement and technical expertise are required.

Consider the following when deciding to build an independent journal platform:

- What technical and financial resources are available to you?
- Is IT support for software installation and maintenance available and how much does it cost?
- Would you be able to ensure maintenance, security, backing up and updates?
- Would you be able to repair and replace hardware if needed (if the publisher has their own server)?
- Would you be able to support all editorial and publishing workflows, including DOI registration and long-term preservation?
- How many journals would you like to host? If it is only one journal, it might be more cost-effective to use software-as-a-service hosting.
- Draft and maintain documentation explaining in detail the technical set-up and workflows to enable an easy transition in case of technical failure, staff change or platform migration.

Software-as-a-Service hosting

In this scenario, a commercial or non-commercial service provider collaborates with a publisher to set up a journal management platform and other services. The services offered may range from a fully set up web environment where even the design of web pages is largely predefined (e.g. OpenEdition, PubPub, Hrčak OJS), to independent and highly customisable instances of the software (e.g. [Open Journals System](#) and [Janeway](#)). They can be offered free of charge or as packages priced based on the service offerings.

Advantages:

- Little or no technical skills are required to set up the platform.
- The service provider takes care about security, backing up, software maintenance, updates, configuring HTML meta tags and XML sitemaps, registering DOIs and setting up metadata exchange protocols (e.g. [Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting - OAI-PMH](#)).

Disadvantages

- Limited customisation options (either because they are not foreseen or because they are offered at a higher price).
- The uptake of emerging best practices is determined by the service provider's capacity to implement them.

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

- Migration to another platform can be difficult, resulting in data loss.

Consider the following when deciding on the hosting option:

- Does the offered service include all the required features? What are the scope and quality of offered services?
- Is long-term preservation ensured by the service provider?
- Are the documentation and technical support provided?
- Are customisations possible? If yes, under what conditions (who can do this; costs)?
- Is it guaranteed that there is no risk of vendor lock-in and is it possible to move the platform to other vendors or to the organisation itself without loss of information or high costs?
- Make sure that hosting is compliant with relevant data protection regulations (e.g. [GDPR](#)).

Once you have chosen appropriate hosting and software solutions, follow the instructions of software providers to set up journal pages and workflows.

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14) Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent

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Introduction
These guidelines will help Diamond OA publishers and journals implement the <i>Diamond Open Access Standard's</i> (DOAS) requirements and recommendations regarding metadata and full text formats.

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

The following topics are covered:

- how to make sure that article-level metadata are complete, rich, readable to humans and machines and exposed in a way that facilitates their use and dissemination;
- cited references as metadata and open metadata initiatives (I4OC and I4OA)
- displaying persistent identifiers
- registering a DOI;
- full-text formats.

Please note that the guidelines explain requirements and recommendations in general terms, while platform-specific technical instructions can be found in the list of references.

Body

Displaying the core metadata

According to DOAS, journals should clearly display the core article metadata on article landing pages:

- article title(s),
- full names and institutional affiliations of authors,
- abstracts
- keywords
- journal title
- ISSN and/or eISSN
- the publisher's name
- publication date
- article number and volume, issue and pagination (if used)
- funding information (as a minimum the name of the funder and the grant number/identifier) and preferably the funder's persistent identifier ([ROR](#))
- information about the open access status, copyright holder and licensing
- persistent identifiers for the publication ([DOI](#)), authors and contributors ([ORCID](#)) and preferably for author affiliations ([ROR](#)).

It is also recommended to indicate author roles (e.g. according to the [CRediT](#) taxonomy) on the article landing page and in the full text.

If a journal is published using an online journal management system, the metadata entered into the system in the publishing process will be automatically displayed on article landing pages. Metadata should be accurate and complete (e.g. affiliations should contain the full name and address of the institution) and all persistent identifiers and the license information should be displayed as active links in line with relevant guidelines.

Metadata should also be machine-readable, which is achieved by embedding them into the source code of web pages as HTML meta tags and exposing them via metadata exchange protocols in standard metadata formats (e.g. XML, JSON, HTML, CSV). Meta tags make it easier for search engines like Google to index web pages. In commonly used free and open source (FOSS) journal management systems (Open Journal Systems, Janeway), meta tags can be automatically generated if the system is properly configured and/or the necessary plugins are used.

Some FOSS journal management systems (OJS, Janeway) support [Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting \(OAI-PMH\)](#) and can expose structured metadata in the XML format, making it possible for aggregators (e.g. BASE, OpenAIRE) to harvest large amounts of metadata at once.

To ensure optimal dissemination, metadata should be released in the public domain (e.g. by using Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Dedication license). Diamond OA publishers and journal editors should make sure that the license is clearly indicated on the website, along with the OAI-PMH endpoint (the URL where the structured metadata are exposed) and/or any instructions on how to harvest metadata.

Tips:

- If the metadata are provided in multiple languages, create a dedicated web page for each language.
- To check whether meta tags are properly configured, use the “View page source” option in the browser or try to capture metadata using a standard reference management application (e.g. Zotero).
- Use an OAI-PMH validator (e.g. [OAI-PMH Validator](#), [Oval](#)) to check whether the protocol is properly configured.
- If the Diamond OA publisher or journals is planning to use a journal management software on the software-as-a-service basis [see Choosing a platform], they should ask whether the service provider has enabled meta tags and metadata exchange protocols.

Cited references

Displaying a list of references on the article landing page, along with the core metadata, is highly recommended. References must conform to a citation style specified in the author guidelines. When deciding which citation style to use in their journals(s), Diamond OA publishers and journals should give preference to those that include DOI or URL in reference list entries (e.g. APA, Chicago) and always display DOIs and URLs as links.

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

Registering DOIs

In order to assign DOIs to articles, Diamond OA publishers should make an arrangement with a DOI [registration agency](#) or a DOI service provider (organisation authorised to register DOIs), which usually involves a membership fee and a fee charged for each DOI. When registering a DOI, article metadata are deposited in a DOI registry. This should be done at the moment when the article is published online, without delay. In some FOSS journal management systems (OJS, Janeway), DOI registration is automated, which means that DOIs can be registered within the system.

The deposited metadata should be rich: include abstracts, persistent identifiers and cited references, and make abstracts and references open in line with the Initiative for Open Abstracts and the Initiative for Open Citations. If you are unable to ensure this now due to limited resources or any other reason, this should be a high priority for the future.

Full-text formats

Most publishers provide full text only in the camera-ready PDF format and the quality of files varies. Here are some tips on how to improve the quality and usability of PDFs:

- Make sure that PDF files are compliant with the PDF/A standard. This can be done by setting up export options in the text editor.
- Use open-source fonts that support Unicode.
- Don't convert text to outlines when creating PDF files.
- Don't limit access to the PDF version of the article (e.g. by setting passwords or restricting printing, copying, etc.)

The *Diamond Open Access Standard* (DOAS) recommends providing the full text of the published articles in multiple formats, at least one of which is suitable for long-term preservation. This can be achieved by tagging full-text content in the XML JATS and then converting it to PDF, HTML and/or ePub. XML JATS files should include structured article metadata, as well as the CRediT information and conflict of interest statements.

Diamond OA publishers who cannot afford XML JATS coding should include it in their plans for the future and should keep exploring available options (e.g. new tools or service providers offering this service at an affordable fee).

Tips:

- All persistent identifiers used in the full text should be displayed as active links.
- Include copyright and license information in the full text. Display the license as an active link.

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15) Marketing, communication and visibility

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Introduction
<p>These guidelines will help Diamond OA publishers and journals implement the <i>Diamond Open Access Standard's</i> (DOAS) requirements regarding visibility and discoverability of the published content, and recommended communication and marketing strategies. By employing a combination of these strategies, Diamond OA publishers and journal editors can significantly increase the visibility, discoverability and impact of their journals, ensuring that the research they publish reaches the largest, most relevant audience possible and has a significant impact.</p>
Body
<p>Visibility</p> <p>Here are several strategies that Diamond OA publishers and journal editors can implement to enhance journal visibility</p> <p>Enhancing openness</p> <p>Freely accessible content increases publisher and journal visibility and the likelihood that the published content will be read and have an impact. Although published articles in open access journals are directly accessible, visibility can be increased by publishing related datasets alongside research articles, ensuring that data are available for verification,</p>

replication, and further analysis. Sharing additional materials such as software, protocols, and methodologies further enhances the transparency and usefulness of research.

Providing clearly stated licensing terms helps users understand how they can legally share and reuse the content. [Creative Commons](#) licenses (e.g., CC BY) are commonly used to allow free distribution and reuse of open access content while respecting authorship rights.

Additionally, article features can be enhanced by including supplementary materials such as videos, audio summaries, interactive data visualisations, and other multimedia materials. To enhance openness, encourage authors to deposit preprints and published content in institutional, multidisciplinary, or subject-specific open repositories.

Transparency of editorial policies

Editorial documents play a crucial role in improving the journal's visibility and overall standing within the academic and research community. Clearly defined and easy-to-understand mission, vision and scope statements; guidelines; and editorial policies enable consistent and effective communication in all marketing efforts.

A clearly articulated *mission statement* defines the journal's purpose and goals, making it clear to potential authors, readers, and reviewers what the journal aims to achieve. A strong mission resonates with researchers who are aligned with the same goals, encouraging them to submit high-quality manuscripts. The mission helps in crafting marketing messages that highlight the journal's contributions to the field. It can be used to attract a dedicated readership and engage with communities interested in the journal's focus areas.

A compelling *vision statement* outlines the journal's long-term purpose and aspirations. It guides the journal's strategic decisions, including editorial directions, partnerships, and innovations that can boost visibility over time.

A well-defined *scope* clearly communicates the areas and types of research the journal publishes and contributes to ensure that submissions are relevant and in line with the journal's focus. Consistently publishing within a clear scope helps build a strong reputation and credibility in specific research domains, leading to higher visibility among experts in those fields.

Clear, comprehensive *author guidelines* ensure that submissions meet the journal's requirements. They can also include instructions on writing for visibility, such as compelling titles and abstract writing strategies.

Reviewer guidelines help ensure high-quality, constructive feedback, improving the overall standard of publications, which in turn enhances the journal's reputation and visibility. In addition, a detailed description of the rigorous and transparent peer review process employed to maintain high standards and attract quality submissions should be provided.

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

Findability / Discoverability

Findability/discoverability focuses on making the journal and its articles easy to locate, particularly by those searching for specific topics. Improving findability enhances visibility, and visibility attracts more engagement.

Register with indexes, library catalogues, discovery tools and aggregators

Submit the journal to widely used and popular multidisciplinary indexing services, and others relevant to the journal's field. Identify and target niche databases and indexes that are disciplinary relevant and cater specifically to the journal's subject matter.

Establish partnerships with libraries to ensure journal inclusion in library catalogues and discovery services. Engage with content aggregators, archives, and databases that compile and provide access to academic content from multiple publishers and distribute it to libraries and other users.

Enable interoperability

Register the journal in institutional or other open repositories that support the [Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting](#) (OAI-PMH). Adhere to globally accepted metadata standards to ensure compatibility and ease of information exchange.

Metadata Quality and Persistent Identifiers

Ensure each article includes complete and accurate metadata (titles, abstracts, keywords, author information, etc.). This aids both search engines and databases in indexing the content effectively.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are essential tools in enhancing the visibility and discoverability of academic journals and their content. They enhance the discoverability of research outputs by providing a permanent and unambiguous way to reference and access digital or physical objects. Persistent identifiers make it easier for search engines, databases, and repositories to index and retrieve content accurately, improving search results. PIDs enable robust cross-linking between articles, datasets, and supplementary materials, enhancing discoverability within and across platforms. Integration of PIDs into submission, peer review, and publication workflows streamlines administrative processes, reducing errors and manual work. Widely used PIDs are [Digital Object Identifier](#) (DOI), [Open Researcher and Contributor ID](#) (ORCID), [International Standard Name Identifier](#) (ISNI), [Research Organization Registry](#) (ROR) and [Open Funder Registry](#) (OFR).

- DOIs provide permanent and stable links to digital content, which ensures that published articles can always be located, even if the URLs change over time. They facilitate accurate citation tracking and metrics, allowing authors and journals to

measure the impact of their work more effectively. DOIs enable interoperability between different indexing services, repositories, and databases, making it easier to aggregate data about the articles. Ensure that each article and possibly each figure, underlying data, or dataset within an article has a DOI.

- ORCID IDs uniquely identify authors, disambiguating them from other researchers with similar names. This ensures that all contributions by a particular author are correctly attributed. ORCID IDs facilitate collaboration and networking by providing a persistent link to an author's complete professional profile and publication history.
- Identifiers for institutions (such as ISNI or ROR) help accurately attribute research outputs to the affiliated institution. They enable more accurate data aggregation for institutional research assessments and bibliometric analyses.
- OFR identifiers (formerly FundRef) help link research outputs to specific grant funding organisations, making it easier to track the impact of funded research. A long-term plan is to deprecate the OFR and merge it with ROR in order to make workflows more efficient for all concerned.
- Persistent identifiers for research data (such as DataCite DOIs) ensure that datasets can be reliably located and accessed, promoting data sharing and reuse. Assigning PIDs to software and tools used in research ensures that all components of the research process are identifiable, cross-linked and citable.

Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

Diamond OA publishers can best ensure SEO by using best practices, such as relevant and specific keywords in titles, abstracts, and throughout the articles, to improve discoverability. Make the journal's website well-structured and navigable, which helps search engines index the content effectively. Keep the website content fresh and updated to encourage search engines to crawl the site more frequently. Ensure the journal's website is optimised for search engines, including HTML tags, sitemaps, and mobile-friendly design.

Linking and Citations

Establish proper internal and external linking practices to interconnect related articles to aid discoverability. Provide easy to be copied and used citations in different citation styles. Encourage proper networking practices where other researchers cite your journal's articles, creating inbound links that boost visibility and discoverability.

Marketing and Communication

Marketing and communication efforts by various stakeholders, such as publishers, editors, authors, and reviewers, are crucial in improving a journal's visibility and findability. Each stakeholder can contribute uniquely to enhancing the reach and impact of the journal's content.

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

Publishers

Implement targeted marketing campaigns through email newsletters, social media, and scholarly conferences. Highlight special issues, high-impact articles, and new developments in the journal. Distribute press releases for groundbreaking studies published in the journal to reach a broader audience, including journalists, researchers, the general public and policymakers.

Ensure social media and online presence by utilising platforms like X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, Mastodon, Facebook, and academic networks to promote published content. Maintain a blog or website to highlight new publications, summarise key findings, and share relevant news. Send regular newsletters featuring new articles, editor's picks, and upcoming journal events to a curated list of subscribers.

Present journal articles at conferences and workshops and support the publication of conference proceedings. Establish partnerships with relevant academic networks, professional societies, and institutions to attract quality submissions and widen the journal's reach.

Become involved in promotion and marketing by writing and distributing press releases for notable articles and engaging with the academic community through webinars, discussions, and forums. Promote articles in related journals and partner with those journals for cross-marketing opportunities.

Editors

Publish guest editorials or special issues on trending topics in the field, which can attract more attention and citations. Still, overusing special issues and possible unwelcome consequences should be considered. Provide clear guidelines on how authors can enhance the visibility of their work. Support authors in promoting their published work through social media kits, promotional videos, or infographics.

Encourage reviewers to share and discuss high-quality articles within their networks and at conferences. Organise webinars, panel discussions, and workshops related to the journal's focus area to build a community of engaged reviewers, readers and contributors.

Authors

Authors can self-promote their published articles on personal social media accounts and academic profiles. They also inform colleagues and collaborators about new publications via email, academic meetings, and conferences.

Authors should be encouraged to deposit their published articles in the institution's repository to improve accessibility and compliance with open access mandates. They can

also present their research at webinars, academic conferences, and public talks to raise awareness and drive readership.

Reviewers

Provide constructive feedback to ensure the articles published are of high quality, enhancing the journal's reputation and attractiveness to new researchers. Recommend the journal and its high-quality articles to peers, students, and at academic events. When appropriate, cite articles from the journal to increase the journal's citation metrics.

General Communication Strategies

Create video abstracts, podcasts, and infographics summarising key articles to attract a wider audience. Host live or recorded webinars where authors discuss their work. Cross-promote articles in related journals and collaborate on joint special issues or thematic series. Participate in academic events, raising the journal profile within relevant academic communities. Engage with subscribers through interactive content like surveys and feedback forms to understand their interests and improve the journal accordingly.

Visual identity

A strong visual identity is a powerful tool for improving the visibility and perception of a publisher and its journals. By creating a consistent, professional, and recognizable brand through logos, colours, and other visual elements, publishers can differentiate themselves in a crowded market, build trust and credibility, and enhance their marketing efforts.

Here's how visual identity can improve visibility:

- Distinctive and consistent use of logos and imagery across all platforms (websites, social media, printed materials) helps in building a recognizable brand.
- Consistent use of colours helps create a visual linkage between different communications and publications from the same publisher.
- A well-designed website with a coherent visual identity improves the user experience, making it easier to navigate and find content, thereby increasing engagement and return visits.
- A visual identity that reflects the journal's thematic focus (e.g., green colours for environmental journals) reinforces the subject matter and appeals to the target audience.
- Eye-catching graphics make social media posts more engaging and shareable, widening the reach of the content. Branded visuals also make it easy for followers to recognize and share official posts, amplifying their impact.
- Branded materials like banners, brochures, and presentations at conferences and different events increase visibility among attendees.

D4.3 IPSP Guidelines

- Consistently branded emails and newsletters ensure that communications are noticed and not lost in the recipient's inbox. Recognizable branding can increase the open and click-through rates of such communications.

A consistent visual identity reinforces the perception of the publisher as organized, professional, and credible. When a publisher invests in a strong, professional visual identity, it suggests that they are equally committed to the quality of the content they publish.

Tips:

- Design a professional logo. Ensure the logo is visible in all formats (digital and print) and incorporates elements that reflect the publisher's mission and values.
- Create a comprehensive style guide that outlines the use of logos, colour schemes, typography, and other visual elements to ensure consistency across all publications and marketing materials.
- Invest in high-quality images that can be used across various platforms.
- Consistently apply the visual identity across websites, social media, email newsletters, conference materials, and promotional items.
- If resources allow, work with professional designers to develop a cohesive and high-impact visual identity. Professional input can greatly enhance the quality and effectiveness of branding efforts.

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16) Usage and metrics

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Contributor(s)
Peer reviewer(s)
Xenia van Edig
Introduction
<p>These guidelines will help Diamond OA publishers and journals implement the <i>Diamond Open Access Standard's</i> (DOAS) requirements regarding usage and metrics.</p> <p>The implementation of comprehensive, accurate, and reliable usage and metric indicators, along with clear communication about analytical tools and methodologies, allows Diamond OA publishers and journals to ensure that all its journals maintain high standards of transparency and accountability. Compliance with data protection regulations further safeguards user privacy and enhances the credibility of the collected data and resultant metrics.</p>
Body
<p>Assessing a journal's quality and impact of published content, particularly in the context of open access (OA) and open science, requires a varied approach. Traditional metrics remain relevant, but responsible metrics have emerged to capture the broader influence and reach of open access publications.</p> <p>Responsible metrics highlight the importance of a balanced, transparent, and inclusive approach to evaluating research. By employing a diverse array of metrics, integrating qualitative assessments, and prioritising transparency and fairness, responsible metrics aim to more accurately reflect the multifaceted impact of scholarly work. By adopting this approach, Diamond OA journals and publishers support the broader goals of open science, promoting an environment where research can be freely shared, accessed, and valued based on an assessment of its actual impact. These measures should capture the academic influence through citations and the broader societal impact through downloads, mentions, and engagement on various platforms.</p>

To support diversity and inclusivity in measuring the impact, it is recommended to avoid Journal Impact Factor (JIF) as a single measure of journal quality and impact of the published content. Instead, Diamond OA publishers and journals should use a variety of quantitative and qualitative indicators to capture a broader spectrum of research impact, including citation metrics, altmetrics, peer reviews, and societal impact measures. There is also a need to recognise that different disciplines have different norms and impact measures.

It is recommended that the methodologies behind metrics be transparent and understandable so that researchers know how their work is evaluated. Selected metrics should use open datasets whenever possible to allow verification and further analysis by the academic community.

Complementing quantitative metrics with qualitative evidence, such as peer review comments, case studies, and expert opinions, to provide context for the numbers can ensure narrative context. In this sense, open peer review, providing free access to the reviewer's reports, should be given more consideration and adopted whenever possible.

The metrics used should be regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changes in the research environment and technological advancements. These metrics can indicate impact (which can be based on citations or alternative metrics), usage, or efficiency of editorial workflow and decisions (like submission, acceptance and publication dates or rejection rates). The granularity of these metrics can also vary, as they may relate to specific content items like articles or the entire publication.

Citation Metrics

Counting the total number of times an article is cited in other scholarly works.

Altmetrics

Tracking how often research is mentioned or shared on social networking platforms like X, LinkedIn, and Facebook. Monitoring appearances in blogs, news articles, and other media sources. Measuring how often articles are saved or bookmarked in reference managers like Mendeley. Tracking engagement through comments on publisher websites, discussion forums, and academic networks.

PIDs are crucial for calculating alternative metrics (altmetrics), which track online attention and engagement.

Usage Metrics

To comprehensively measure a journal's impact and its published content, especially in the context of open access and open science, it is essential to use a combination of traditional and alternative metrics (altmetrics). These measures should capture the academic influence

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through usage and the broader societal impact through downloads, mentions, and engagement on various platforms. Implementing these diverse metrics enables a holistic view of the journal's reach, influence, and contribution to the scientific community and society.

IPs should provide metric indicators at the article and journal level, including visits, views, downloads and citations, altmetric data and geographical distribution of visitors. These metrics may require different levels of effort, technical expertise, and support, or they may involve financial resources. Some metrics are relatively undemanding from a technical perspective, such as recording submission, acceptance, and publication dates, while others may necessitate special software or plugins, like widgets displaying the geographical distribution of visitors. Finally, some metrics represent proprietary solutions that could require funding, such as Altmetric, PlumX Metrics, or Dimensions citation badges.

Editorial workflow

The editorial workflow is fundamental to maintaining the quality, timeliness, and integrity of scholarly publishing. It benefits all stakeholders involved (authors, reviewers, editors, and readers) by ensuring that research reports are disseminated smoothly, effectively, and ethically, maintaining high standards of scholarly rigour.

There are several components of the editorial workflow that can be monitored and measured, like timeliness of the initial review of manuscript submission (checks for completeness and adherence to submission guidelines, ensuring that the manuscript fits the journal scope and meets basic quality standards), assignment to an editor or associate editor with relevant expertise, selection of appropriate reviewers and management of the peer review process, supervision of the revisions and resubmission of the revised manuscript, the decision on final acceptance, copyediting, formatting and proofing, typesetting and layout, assignment of persistent identifiers ([DOI](#) etc.), publication of articles, distribution and indexing in relevant databases, promotion and dissemination of the published content, and monitoring the impact metrics.

The efficiency of the editorial workflow can be measured by the turnaround time of submission to decisions, reviewer response time and quality of reviews, editorial decision consistency and fairness, the number of appeals and their outcomes, production speed, and author and reviewer satisfaction. To improve the editorial workflow, the time between different stages of the editorial process should be continuously evaluated, tracked and measured, the quality of the peer review and author revisions should be assessed, as well as author and reviewer satisfaction. It is important to identify stages in the editorial workflow where delays frequently occur and implement strategies for improvement. Continuous evaluation of the editorial management system and other technologies (plagiarism checks,

automatic reminders, etc.) should be in place.

Analytical Tools

An analytical tool refers to a combination of measuring, acquiring data, analyzing, and reporting on data to estimate journal usage, impact, and metrics. By using analytical tools, journals can gain a comprehensive understanding of their usage, impact, and influence within the academic community and beyond. Besides the quality of published content and editorial workflow, the information provided by analytical tools is crucial for improving journal policies, enhancing visibility, and demonstrating value to authors, readers, and funders.

Most used analytical tools are based on popular citation databases, like [Web of Science Core Collection](#) (WoSCC) and Scopus, providing various metric indicators. Elsevier's analytical tool [SciVal](#) provides visualisation of the research performance, benchmarking relative to peers, and allows for trend analysis. The visibility and impact of journals in different disciplines can also be assessed by the freely accessible, but not always reliable, [Google Scholar](#) (GS) citation metrics.

Different analytical tools go beyond citations and track online attention and discussions around scholarly articles, including mentions on social media, news outlets, policy documents and blogs, like Altmetric. Besides citations and mentions/reactions on social media, Plum Analytics offers a range of metrics on usage and captures (export/saves, readers, bookmarks, favourites). Recently, Dimensions has offered a research insights platform that integrates different data sources to provide metrics on publications, citations, grants, patents, clinical trials, and policy documents.

Although many popular analytical tools are available only at high subscription prices, there are also free analytical tools, like [CORE](#), which aggregates open-access research outputs and provides metrics on their usage and impact, [VOSviewer](#) and [CiteSpace](#) for bibliometric analysis, [Open Access Button](#) (offering also tools for libraries), and various tools for usage data on institutional repositories. Additionally, commercial analytical tools sometimes offer a limited free version, offer freely accessible browser extensions ([Altmetric](#), [Unpaywall](#)) or free access to a subset of features and data ([Dimensions](#)). There are also publisher-specific tools available, like [CrossRef Metadata Search](#), providing citation links and some basic metrics.

Diamond OA publishers ensure transparency about the analytical tools and methodologies used to collect, generate, and analyze data, providing the description of tools, algorithms, and methodologies used. With respect to GDPR Compliance, they must ensure that all data collection and processing activities comply with relevant data protection regulations, such as the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR) in Europe. It is necessary to implement measures to protect the privacy of users whose data is being collected. This includes

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anonymizing data where applicable and ensuring secure data storage.

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Further reading

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17) Gender diversity

Lead author(s)

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Peer reviewer(s)

Elio Pellin, Laura Rincón

Introduction

As a companion document to the toolsuite on gender equity, these guidelines provide some practical suggestions to help Diamond OA publishers and service providers integrate gender equity into their activities. These guidelines include the recommendations laid out in the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) (Rico-Castro et al. 2024). Given that each IPSP may be at a different stage of integrating gender equity practices, and that each IPSP may have

different resources at their disposal, the guidelines have been organized into three broad categories:

- A. Easy to accomplish:** So-called “quick wins”, these are practices that can be implemented relatively quickly and easily and need few resources.
- B. Moderate investments for the mid-term:** These practices may require more effort or resources to implement than the “quick wins”, but overall these investments are relatively modest and can be achieved without significant costs.
- C. Longer term goals:** These practices may require additional planning or resources, or may need to be developed over a longer period of time.

Within each category, an attempt has been made to organize the suggestions from most easy to accomplish/least resource-intensive to most challenging/resource-intensive. It is important to note that this list of guidelines is suggestive, rather than comprehensive, and the suggestions may not be equally relevant to all IPSPs.

Body

A. Easy to accomplish:

1. Raise awareness, provide information and/or basic training about unconscious bias and how to avoid it (e.g. to authors, peer reviewers, editors and editorial board members, employees).
2. Encourage the use of inclusive language and images when preparing a manuscript to ensure that gender disparities are not unconsciously reinforced through terminological or image choices.
3. Encourage the use of gender neutral or gender-inclusive language when preparing peer review or editorial feedback.
4. Craft and share an equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) statement that addresses gender diversity to signal to authors and readers that the IPSP/journal values and seeks out a range of perspectives.

B. Moderate investments for the mid-term:

1. Seek out an appropriately gender-diverse pool of authors, reviewers, editors and board members, track progress and make an action plan. Once a gender-diverse pool of reviewers has been established, be sure to solicit reviews from the various genders in appropriate proportions.
2. Offer authors and peer reviewers the option to self-report their gender (and include non-binary options), and monitor and track progress towards meeting diversity goals. However, note that some authors may not wish to self-report, and in such cases, it is important to respect their privacy.
3. Implement a policy requiring authors to submit a citation diversity statement.
4. Implement a policy to ensure that authors include a suitable representation of sex/gender in research subjects/study populations, and that they report on this

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aspect appropriately. For some types of study (e.g. health research), not reporting on gender could reduce the usefulness of the findings for some populations. However, note that some study participants may not wish to report their gender, and their right to privacy must be respected.

5. Implement double-anonymous review (author and reviewer are unknown to one another) to reduce reviewer gender bias

C. Longer term goals:

1. Conduct an author diversity audit regularly (e.g. using a survey).
2. Consider open review (where authors and reviewers are aware of the other's identity) as a means of promoting inclusion by inviting a wide community to comment BUT consider whether this openness may disadvantage some authors (e.g. those who belong to a disadvantaged gender minority).
3. Hire and retain gender-diverse employees (including in senior positions) because homogeneous environments foster homogeneous attitudes and practices.

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18) Multilingualism

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Peer reviewer(s)

Elio Pellin, Laura Rincón

Introduction

As a companion document to the toolsuite on multilingualism, these guidelines provide some practical suggestions to help Diamond OA publishers and service providers integrate multilingualism into their activities. These guidelines include the recommendations laid out in the *Diamond Open Access Standard* (DOAS) (Rico- Castro et al. 2024). Given that each Diamond OA publisher and service provider may be at a different stage of integrating multilingual practices, and that each Diamond OA publisher and service provider may have different resources at their disposal, the guidelines have been organized into three broad categories:

- A. Easy to accomplish:** So-called “quick wins”, these are practices that can be implemented relatively quickly and easily and need few resources.

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B. Moderate investments for the mid-term: These practices may require more effort or resources to implement than the “quick wins”, but overall these investments are relatively modest and can be achieved without significant costs.

C. Longer term goals: These practices may require additional planning or resources, or may need to be developed over a longer period of time.

Within each category, an attempt has been made to organize the suggestions from most easy to accomplish/least resource-intensive to most challenging/resource-intensive. It is important to note that this list of guidelines is suggestive, rather than comprehensive, and the suggestions may not be equally relevant to all IPSPs.

Body

A. Easy to accomplish:

1. Develop a policy statement confirming that submissions within the thematic scope and language of the journal are accepted from all potential authors and that decision-making concerning content is without regard to their language background.
2. Include a statement on the peer review feedback form indicating that linguistic quality alone is not a sufficient reason for rejecting a submission.
3. Develop a policy requiring authors to report whether the research data are sensitive to language.
4. Identify affordable, reputable editing and translation services with whom your organization can work effectively and make the contact details for these services available to potential authors.
5. Raise awareness about unconscious linguistic bias and point authors, peer reviewers, editors and journal staff members towards existing relevant resources to help them minimize their own unconscious bias.
6. Raise awareness about clear writing and translation friendly style, and point authors towards existing resources that can be used to develop (machine) translation friendly abstracts and articles.
7. Revise the content of the website, guidelines, policies and other communications so that they are written in a (machine) translation friendly style (i.e., clear and unambiguous language). Ensure that all future communications are also prepared in a translation friendly style.
8. Raise awareness about linguistic citation diversity (i.e., citing work in other languages), and point authors to existing guidelines about how to cite work in other languages.
9. Develop a policy requiring authors to submit a linguistic citation diversity statement with their manuscript.
10. Include linguistic citation diversity as an item to be evaluated on peer review feedback forms.

11. Integrate an automatic translation tool (e.g. via a translation widget) into the website, with appropriate caveats.

B. Moderate investments for the mid-term:

1. Request and publish plain language summaries (written in a translation friendly style) alongside scientific abstracts on the website and/or in journal articles.
2. Publish abstracts in at least two languages.
3. Develop (or refine) clear guidelines regarding permission to publish the same or similar works in other languages elsewhere (with acknowledgement of the original publication). Strive to be as permissive as possible and make sure that the guidelines are easy for authors to find and understand.
4. Set goals for diverse linguistic representation among editorial board members and peer reviewers, and monitor progress towards the goals.
5. Create an explicit recognition mechanism to credit translators for their work (e.g. include a by-line field under the author's name, or generate a certificate as some publishers already do for peer reviewers).
6. Deliver peer review training sessions or provide peer review guidelines in multiple languages.

C. Longer term goals:

1. Publish abstracts and full-texts in two or more languages in the same document or as separate documents, if the authors provide the translations.
2. Develop a mechanism for collecting and monitoring the number/proportion of abstracts and full texts that are multilingual and make this information available.
3. Publish content in a machine-translation friendly format (e.g. in HTML instead of only in PDF) to make it easier for researchers who want to engage with the content via machine translation tools.
4. Translate the website, policies, guidelines, and calls for papers into at least one additional language and ensure that the same information is provided in all languages.
5. Provide English-language metadata in cases where the language of the text is not English.
6. Subsidize or fully support professional translation and language-check services for authors.

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5. Annex 2: Guidelines template

Guideline Title

Lead author(s)
Name(s) of lead author(s)
Contributor(s)
Name(s) of other author(s)
Peer reviewer(s)
Name(s) of other peer reviewer(s)
Introduction
A short abstract presenting the topic and scope of the article
Body
500-word article that provides information and practical instructions on the addressed topic.
References
List of references in bullet points
Further reading
List of further reading in bullet points
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